

Organized Crime a Specific Approach

Artur Victoria

If the basic characterization of organized crime is to be found, one can find, among scholars of the subject, quite unanimity - the same is no longer the case with the precise definition of the concept:

In fact, it is difficult to establish a final concept on organized crime when, on the one hand, it is faced with multiple and renewed criminal practices, triggered by groups or networks in permanent dynamic adaptation and, on the other hand, we find "users" with varying degrees of conceptual demand and practical requirements, depending on the different purposes pursued: criminal investigation, criminal prosecution, exercise of legislative power, etc.

In fact, the investigator will be particularly interested in the objective screening of the organized criminal structure that he intends to dismantle, the magistrate the legal and penal framework of the criminal occurrences that occurred and their insertion in the legal figures created by the legislator (who, in fact, in Portugal, at no time) uses the expression "organized crime" in the current legislative frameworks, rather opting for "close" figures such as that of the "Criminal Association" (arts. 2874. of the Penal Code) or "Association of Delinquents" (art. 284. of the Decree) Law 430/83).

Origin and evolution of the organized crime

Organized criminal practice dates back to other centuries, being referenced, for example, in England, at the beginning of the sec. - XVIII (case of the group controlled by Jonathan Wild that was dedicated to theft, robbery and extortion in the city of London).

However, organized crime in the Modern Era found its roots in the 1920s / 30s, with the Institution of the "Prohibition Act" ("Volstead Act) in the USA, which prohibited the manufacture and consumption of alcohol - causing the emergence of groups for smuggling in territorial parcels defined by force, and dedicated to the distribution and smuggling of alcoholic beverages to the USA, from Europe and Canada. And the time of the "gangs", directed some of them by characters ("gangsters") already very romanticized, like, for example, Al Capone.

In the following decades (years, 30/40/50), these "gangs" evolved into other areas of equally lucrative activity and that, gradually, dominated: illegal gambling; prostitution (pimping); extortion ("protection tax"); infiltration of labor unions; the smuggling of various consumer products and, finally, in the 1960s, devoting himself to what still

constitutes his main source of income today: major trafficking, namely the illicit trafficking in narcotics.

During the past 70 years, organized crime has specialized in stabilizing its fields and methods of action, developing true “multinationals of crime” with structures and power of action that have long gone beyond the established national borders.

Nowadays, almost instinctively, organized crime is associated with “Mafia” groups or terrorist groups - not only because, in fact, they will represent the maximum exponent of organized criminal expression, but also because they are always avid media phenomena. sought, transmitted and developed by the media.

1.2 RATINGS

We can distinguish and classify organized crime according to two broad categories, taking as a differentiating criterion the motivations and objectives that are finally pursued by their action.

- With motivations and objectives for profit
- With dominant political motivations and objectives

For the groups located in the first of the categories mentioned above, organized crime is fundamentally a big deal, while for those in the second, organized crime practices constitute a fundamental form of expression and combat. really well.

However, and as is evident, there will always be confluences and inter-penetration of interests and objectives - tactical and / or strategic, occasional or temporary - between agents in the world of organized crime. An example of this assertion is transmitted to us by the so-called "NARCOTERRORISM": in several Latin American countries, drug traffickers, in order to better implement and protect their action and scope, persecute and violently pressure the political power and instituted governments, through actions typically terrorists.

Specific characterization

The degree of organization and complexity of a criminal structure will depend, among other factors, on the size (number of members, territory of action, level of coverage (for legal) and the type of activity of each organization.

The type structure of an organized crime group often represented by the "Pyramid": a narrow "top" and a broad "base", graphically signifying, on the one hand, the numerical distribution of the members of the group and, on the other hand, the their level of responsibility and involvement in it.

This organized crime network is spread over four levels, with Level 1 corresponding to Leader, with leadership capacity and strategic decision-making for the group's activity and made up of a small number of individuals.

At level 2, 3, and 4 corresponds to the activity of large, medium and small traffic respectively. As is evident, the degree of insertion and responsibility in the network is attenuating the measure that we descend in the "Pyramid" and that, simultaneously, the number of members involved in the criminal tasks increases.

In turn, an important aspect, the final recipient of the network's action - the drug user - only physically contacts the small dealer located at level 4.

This, in turn, only knows his "contact" at the level on the network next, thus successively reinforcing and protecting, in final terms, the upper levels of organized criminal structures, while the members of the lower links are unaware of the global dimension of the network.

In fact, the level of leadership of an organized drug trafficking network and, as a rule, a complex structure, since it has to lead the correct chain of tasks that, although structurally related to the traffic of the product itself, are prior or subsequent to it, such as the production, transport, storage and distribution of the product and legal - legal coverage of all activities.

Although without great development (which in this work does not reap), we compare and analyze the "type structure" of three distinct, but representative, expressions of organized crime:

- South American "Cartel" dedicated to cocaine trafficking;
- Italian mob group ("Cosa Nostra");
- European (urban) terrorist group.

Although the motivations and final objectives of these three organized crime groups are diverse - the first two seek, through the practice of various illicit acts, with a preponderance for the trafficking of drugs, an economic gain, the third seeks fundamentally the subversion and political - institutional confrontation with the State - in the respective type structures we can identify common features to retain, in summary:

- . Cellular organization of the pyramid type - that is, the greater knowledge of the network works in direct reason of the importance of the place it occupies in it. A member at the "base" level is unaware of the global dimension of the organization, a situation that is only held by the organization's leaders.

- . Existence of several "hierarchical" levels of action and responsibility. In this respect, the structure of "Cosa Nostra" is paradigmatic and "refined", perhaps due to its ancestry as an organization and extreme territorial division of action (neighbourhood). It should also be noted, in the context of terrorist groups, the clear definition of levels of decision and action.

Safety

The degree of effectiveness and stability of a criminal organization is also achieved through the use of security mechanisms, both in terms of its external activity and in terms of its internal functioning.

a) In terms of the preparation and execution of the criminal (external) activity, the use of the following methodologies should be noted:

- . Systematic collection of information: about the enemy (police structures: organization, methods and tactics) about competitors (other criminal organizations), about the "targets", about the collaborators, about their areas of activity "market", - for that purpose using even specialized collection techniques, such as surveillance (by technical and human means), grooming and infiltration;

- . Use of static measures (protection) and active measures (detection and deception) of counter-information;

- . Use of sophisticated communications systems.

b) In terms of the organization's internal regulation, proceed to:

- . Surveillance and "hierarchical" control of members;

- . Adoption of codes of conduct;

- . Use of drastic disciplinary measures against members who have broken the established rules of conduct, reinforced by coercive measures and threats against those who try to violate them, namely when detained;

. Awarding rewards to members who are distinguished for their effectiveness in action and / or loyalty to the organization;

. Guarantee of mutual assistance to members (and their families) in difficult times, such as in detention, in prison or in accessibility to good lawyers.

The multiple delimiting expressions that organized crime assumes do not make it impossible to try to find some common denominators for all of them and that, in the final analysis, will essentially characterize this type of crime.

In methodological terms, the lists of these common properties are according to the following aspects of analysis:

- Structure

- Financing -Security

- Operational development

Structure

This type of crime is structured in an organized way, according to horizontal and vertical vectors.

Thus, in addition to the Structure element - dictating that the relationships between the bottom and the top of the organization are not, as a rule, direct but filtered by the intermediate hierarchy - the Security element, through the aforementioned methodologies, constitutes a common component and characterizing organized crime.

Financing

Any organization, legal or illegal, has operating costs, fixed and variable, needing money for the development of its activities.

In general terms, we can say that in the world of organized crime, the lack of liquidity will certainly not be one of the main concerns - perhaps it would be its excess.

Illegal activities carried out by the organized crime sub-world generate, by system, with greater or lesser frequency, large monetary inflows to criminal organizations, whether at national or transnational level.

International organizations have, for example, estimated that the activities of mafia groups generated, in 2018 their own revenues estimated at around Euro 1 billion in

Hungary, Euro 2 to 3 billion in the USA, PTE 3 billion. tales in the EEC space, 5 billion in Japan.

Where do these recipes come from?

Illegal activities such as drug trafficking, arms trafficking, exploitation of "paid protection" ("racket", extortion), exploitation of contracts or subcontracts in public works, smuggling of various products, gambling, among others.

But also a set of activities of a legal nature, such as businesses involving companies, casinos, financial institutions - which are nothing more than legal "covers" - business created to, in addition to their alleged current activity, circulate and in some way justify the revenues (or part of them) obtained by organizations in an unlawful manner. This is the camouflage methodology.

In addition, organized crime structures control and exploit an illicit "parallel market" (national or transnational), which allows the exchange of a wide variety of products and services: counterfeit coins for drugs, weapons for nuclear technology, cocaine for heroin, etc. But they also exploit the legally established economic and financial market, namely for the consummation of their second financing methodology: money laundering.

Money laundering is understood as a set of operations, fundamentally of a financial nature, which consist of removing the wealth obtained from its illegal source. In making "masses" clean, in the light of society, money masses that, in their origin, are "dirty", because they were obtained illegally. Take the case of, for example, the "Cartel de Cali" which, in the late 2000s, laundered 57 million dollars - of which 36 million will be in Europe - through the creation of numerous ghost and ghost societies consecutive deposit movements in 268 accounts opened at 118 banks in Europe, USA and Panama).

This amount, for all intents and purposes, appears "in fine" as apt to be (re) invested, without suspicion of major, in any economic, commercial, industrial or financial activity of the established market, then criminal organizations function as true "empires" "business.

Thus, the cloaking of activities (relating to people, but also to business) and money laundering (which normally refers to about 30 to 50% of the global revenues obtained by the organization) as a result of multiple other illegal activities previous, always (also) revenue generators, represent another of the most significantly common aspects Organized crime, with regard to its hidden financing.

Operational development

The common denominators inherent in the structure, security and financing of criminal organizations have already made it possible to characterize organized crime substantially.

Still in relation to most organized crime (the exception corresponds, in part, to terrorist organizations), we can add another common element: the type of Operational Development.

The Operational Development of organized crime activities is established, as a rule, according to the following vectors:

- a) Scope of national, international and transnational action;
- b) Permanent and stabilized operability, with tactical and strategic concerns;
- c) Combination of lawful and illicit businesses;
- d) Chronological interaction and multiple offenses.

In previous points, some of these vectors have already been discussed. However, we note here the simultaneous importance of all of them in the operational development of organized crime.

Thus, we can say that:

- a) - The reason for this type of crime will lie in the broad scope of territorial action and in its permanent and stabilized organization in the pursuit of criminal activity;
- b) - The reason for the organizations' effectiveness, in addition to the fulfilment of their ultimate objective (namely, the economic gain), will lie in their malleability in the face of dissuasive circumstances, in their dynamics of tactical and strategic articulation, in their capacity to hide the illicit financing sources (illicit businesses), through the creation and maintenance of Illicit businesses (real or simulated) that, "in fine", allow to justify and "clean up" the global means obtained.

In terms of illicit business / crimes, we can classify as strategic those that, in some way, best allow the "normal" pursuit of the organization's financing activities. The practice of corruption, concealment, traffic of influences and control of the authorities will allow the organization to strategically avoid difficulties and avoid (major) jumps to the operational development of the activity tactically chosen by the organization to make a profit, be it drug trafficking, extortion and kidnappings, arms trafficking (or now also nuclear products), smuggling, among others.

The legal businesses most "sought after" by criminal organizations are located in several sectors, such as: the financial market (holding and / or participation in credit institutions, savings banks, leases, brokerage firms, etc.) and the securities market. capitals - fields par excellence for the practice of large money laundering operations -, casinos and the hotel industry, civil construction and other business activities, such as the establishment of import-export firms (namely based in tax havens).

In fact, the infiltration of organized crime into legal businesses is an additional tactic to effectively reduce the risk of detecting the network, by covering up and legitimizing the revenues produced, which, thus, raise less suspicion as to their possession. Furthermore, the insertion in legitimate commercial activities and operations, namely at the international level, offers criminal organizations the possibility of using routes for the circulation and transportation of non-illegal products for part of their illegal cargo.

c) - the criminal reason for organized crime will lie, on the one hand, in the multiple execution of illicit acts and, on the other hand, in their criminal interaction.

The operational development of organized crime networks favours the practice of multiple criminal offenses, whether from the perspective of their external security - crimes of corruption, trafficking in influences, threats, - or in terms of internal security - crimes of murder, bodily harm, coercion and threats, - whether from the perspective of the disposal of revenues - the crime of money laundering, various counterfeits, tax offenses, etc.

In another perspective, for the vast majority of criminal organizations, the permanent and stabilized practice of one type of crime, such as drug trafficking, is associated with the operational development of other types of crimes such as arms trafficking, automobile traffic, and the traffic of technological components.

The fields of action of organized crime

In the foregoing points, the phenomenon of organized crime was briefly characterized, concluding that, on the concrete level, criminal action was manifested through the plural realization of illicit acts, some more violent, others more cunning.

Organized crime reveals itself in different fields of action, using traditional and / or innovative "modus operandi" and contemplating areas of activity, products and goods with "added value" in society, material as immaterial: human life, security, socio-economic stability, confidence in structures of authority, money, or power.

International perspective

Globally, there is a growing internationalization of organized crime.

The existing communication facilities (favouring the rapid movement of people and goods from one corner of the world to the other or, then, their instant contact by electronic means - fixed and mobile telephone, fax, telex, e-mail, radio, etc.), the intense circulation of products and recipes in international circuits, among other factors, favour the extension of criminal activities by organized groups from several countries, leading to international cooperation and interdependence between national criminal organizations in the countries involved.

The United Nations Congress on crime prevention - it grouped criminal activities with an international character in five major areas: mafia-type activities; terrorist-type activities; fraudulent economic and financial activities; illicit trade activities of art and objects of the cultural heritage of the Nations.

Better realizing the fields of organized criminal action, we can easily identify:

- Terrorist operations;
- (large) traffic operations: drugs, weapons, automobiles, works of art, also of people (for the purpose of sexual or economic exploitation) and, more recently, of nuclear technological components (from Eastern European countries to several Arab countries and emerging regional powers);
- Large-scale counterfeiting operations: currency, credit securities (namely, euro cheques and traveller-checks) and credit cards (namely, "American Express", "Visa" and "Diners Club", particularly in Asia);
- Smuggling operations (very active and in vogue in Eastern European countries and Africa);
- Fraud operations in marine insurance and modern versions of piracy (very active in the seas of China, Hong Kong, Malaysia, Japan);
- Computer crime operations and using new technologies (namely, as instrumental support to complex criminal activities of organized networks).

Organized crime gains its most current (and popular) expression - as mentioned in the previous point 3.3.1. - through terrorist activities, illicit drug trafficking and mobster

activities. In fact, there is a growing tendency for terrorist groups to become involved in the world of organized crime of an entirely non-political nature (as well as the reverse is also true), due to the multiple established criminal interdependencies (examples: narcoterrorism in Latin America; terrorism "cultural" in Italian cities, as a possible form of pressure from the Mafia on the Italian authorities and the State, which are effectively acting in their fight).

Let us analyze, in a little more detail, these three expressions of organized crime.

The Mafia

"MAFIA" is the paradigm of organized crime. In fact, there are those who reduce the concept of this to the "MAFIA" phenomenon.

In fact, there is no MAFIA, but rather several organizations, with different designations and common modes of criminal action generally referred to as "mobsters".

The Italian writer Leonardo Sciascia, about 30 years ago, defined the Mafia as "an association of criminals with the purpose of illicit enrichment of the associates, who stands as an intermediary, imposed by violence, between property and work, between production and consumption, between citizens and the State "while, in another perspective, sociologist Raimondo Catanzaro recently defined it as" the violence industry ".

Evolution

The "MAFIA" (Italian - American) had its origin in Sicily, in the 12th or 13th centuries, assuming ever since as an organized insurrection the successive occupations that this island in the south of Italy has suffered through the ages. Its cultural roots are rural, only transferring to large cities (mainly Palermo) in the first decades of this century, quickly implementing its traditional methods of action: "paid protection", that is, extortion.

First in fairs and markets, then in the sectors of commerce and civil construction, requiring progressively higher percentages from companies and, later, ending up constituting their own construction companies, which came to dominate the market.

However, the decisive factor that still marks its evolution today, happens in the 70s when, with the dismantling of the clandestine laboratories and the networks of the "French Connection" (based in Marseille - South of France), MAFIA takes over the European traffic heroin and corresponding huge profits.

Thus, from a subordinate position (support for the transit of the product through Sicily), it started to process morphine from Asia and the Middle East in its own laboratories and, in a short period of time, reorganized its presence on the

international trafficking scene. It becomes a supplier of 65 to 70% of the heroin consumed in the USA and, in the 90s, it assumes an increasing intervention in the cocaine traffic to Europe. Concomitantly, it was updated and adapted to more "entrepreneurial" and "executive features, to the detriment of its violent" brand image".

Types and methods

Today, it is usual to talk about East Mafia, Turkish Mafia, Japanese Mafia, Chinese Mafia, and others. In fact, we are talking about organized crime groups, which historically and culturally have nothing to do with the Sicilian Mafia, having in common with it only the methods of criminal action.

a) In Italy, organized crime of the Mafia type is divided into four distinct branches, departing from traditional regional borders in southern Italy: "COSA NOSTRA", in Sicily, "CAMORRA", in Naples; "N 'DRANGHETTA", in Calabria; "SACRA CORONA UNITA", in the southeast.

The "Cosa Nostra" is the most important, involving about 140 families that can comprise between 30 to 300 base mobsters, the soldiers or "homo d 'onore". It is an articulated, unitary and hierarchical structure.

The Neapolitan "Camorra" and the Calabrian "N'dranghetta", as well as the "Sacra Corona Unita", do not have this vertically hierarchical and compartmentalized structure, but rather a horizontal structure, with "families" intending to control illegal activities throughout the country. regional action territory (in "Cosa Nostra", to avoid major conflicts, each "family" has its action territory, at the neighborhood level).

The basis of action of these organizations is the traditional activities of extortion ("paid protection"), manipulation of works contracts, illicit drug trafficking and money laundering.

The "N'dranghetta" is the most bloodthirsty and violent, having specialized in kidnappings and rescues, alongside action on the important regional fruit and vegetable markets and oil production, being very active in the traffic of narcotics to areas of the Canada, USA, Australia, South of France and Germany (where we find Calabrian communities).

"Camorra" has converted its cigarette smuggling activities into the most profitable narcotics trafficking activity, assuming an almost monopoly role in cocaine trafficking between South America (namely Peru and Colombia) and Europe, holding "bases" "in several European countries. In the traffic of heroin and hashish, it operates in the smaller spaces left by the activity of "Cosa Nostra", which, in turn, occupies an almost monopoly role in the international traffic of these products to the USA The "Cosa

Nostra" is also dedicated , relevantly, arms trafficking, currency trafficking and money laundering (namely, using credit institutions it controls and companies it has created, mainly in the sectors of civil construction, transport and industry).

b) The Mafia has also long since become an American problem of criminal importance - from the beginning of the century, following the migratory currents of Sicilians to the "New World", many were the "mafiosi" who settled in the USA developing its "families".

The image and structure of the Sicilian parent organization, initially maintaining a "filial" relationship over the years this relationship of subordination has disappeared, giving rise to a complete autonomy of the American "Cosa Nostra", despite the deep collaborative relations that, for common interest, the two organizations maintain.

In fact, some significant differences can be detected: while the Americans have among their main activities the exploitation of gambling houses and prostitution, specializing in the illegal markets, the Sicilians refuse these activities, tending to articulate the action in the illegal markets with a convenient presence in legal markets.

c) In Eastern Europe, economic and political openness, combined with an evident crisis of authority in the various states undergoing democratization, paved the way for the operational development of organized crime.

The Russian Ministry of the Interior counted in activity around 3 000 "gangs" that integrate hundreds of thousands of elements, with ramifications in all social levels. In other territories of the former Soviet Union (namely in the Baltic area), in Poland, Hungary, in former Czechoslovakia and Bulgaria, organized criminal groups have been implanted and have gained active expression.

Rooted in the old "nomenkulatura" or in the groups that then dominated the market, these "Eastern Mafias" are primarily dedicated to drug trafficking (notably in Russia and the Czech Republic), but also in the arms, prostitution and trafficking business. automobiles (mainly in Poland, in view of the territorial contiguity with Germany), as well as the trafficking and smuggling of essential products, medicines, records, cassettes and videos, as well as luxury products (perfumes, watches, precious stones.).

The methods used are close to those of the Sicilian "violence industry" but, however, the structure of these "Eastern Mafias" is not comparable to the hierarchy and organization inherent in the Italian-American "Cosa Nostra".

Russian mafia networks, for example, have an ethnic base in their constitution (Azerbaijani leadership; Chechens as armed operatives; Uzbeks and Tajiks in opium trafficking; Ukrainians and Russians in trafficking in poppy and synthetic drugs; Tatars in gambling, entertainment and terrorism, Georgians in stolen cars, Dagestan in great

banditry), are individualistic and mutually conflicting, without any central control body (except the "Middle" that brings together only 20 large groups in the Moscow area).

However, the growth in drug production, the dynamism of the traffic and money laundering circuits (in Moscow, for example, there are more casinos than in Las Vegas), have already dictated the transformation of cities like Moscow, Prague and Budapest on the nerve-racking world signs of organized crime in general and illicit drug trafficking in particular - giving so-called "Eastern Mafias" increased criminal power and importance, not only in the regional context, but also in the European and worldwide.

d) Two very important forms of organized criminal expression, originating in the East: the "YAKUZA" (or Japanese Mafia) and the "TRIADES" (or Chinese Mafia).

Both represent real criminal sub - cultures, with secular traditions and roots, made up of groups of strict selective recruitment and rigidly disciplined in hierarchically established structures.

The "Yakuza" are entities until recently allowed in Japan. According to statistics from the end of 1991, there were about 3,500 gangs and 91,000 gangsters in Japan, dominated by three large groups: the "Yamaguchi" (the most important, based in the Kansai region, controlling 1330 "Yakuzas" gangs), "Sumiyoshi" and "Inagawa" (both based in Tokyo).

Its main activities are aimed at:

- 1) Control and management of gambling houses and brothels;
- 2) Extortion through "paid protection" ("mikagime-ryo");
- 3) Blackmail with confidential economic, financial or commercial information ("sokaya"). However, the most profitable activities (35% of their income) are drug trafficking, arms trafficking and intervention in the stock exchange (capital market).

They basically operate in Japan and the surrounding areas, beginning in the 1980s to extend their area of action to other areas of the globe, namely to the West.

Its activities have high levels of profitability (for example, the "Yamaguchi" group, in 1991, had more turnover than the multinational "Sony"). This situation that the recent Marco law of 1992, making its main activities illegal, "in fine", had affected only about 20% of the earnings.

Chinese secret societies or "TRIADES" are nowadays a group of criminal organizations with implantation in the Chinese communities ("CHINATOWNS") spread by the main cities of the world. They currently have a "Homeland" which is Hong Kong and several "headquarters": Taiwan, Macau, Burma, Thailand, in the Far East; London, Amsterdam

and Glasgow, Europe; New York, San Francisco and other state capitals in the U.S.; Toronto and Vancouver.

Dominating the markets for cultivation, processing, trafficking in opium and its derivatives (mainly heroin) from the Golden Triangle - (Burma, Laos and Thailand), the countless existing "Triads" supply American, Canadian, English and Dutch cities, through the action of groups of dealers controlled by him (the regular members of the "Triads" are not involved in the distribution of narcotics on the streets).

(When operating outside Hong Kong, "TRIADE" groups are known as "TONGS", particularly in the U.S.)

Heroin trafficking and gambling (namely, Chinese games of chance) are their main source of funding, although they are also involved in criminal extortion activities ("paid protection") to traders, thefts, murders, smuggling, slavery of non-Chinese Asian women destined for prostitution; also, in clandestine banking operations ("shop-shop").

They are organizations with multiseular roots (the Chinese usually say that they invented MAFIA and, later, Marco Polo brought it to the South of Italy), the "Triads" had, in the West, a development sequence similar to the American Mafia. The initial involvement was at the level of street violence, and now the emphasis is placed on increasing the organization's "legitimacy": the objective and moving from open crime to more "legal" operations, using funds obtained illegally to gain access to business legitimate (usually money obtained and "laundered" in Hong Kong or Taiwan and returned to the US or other Western countries as legitimate investments).

Obeying a complex pyramidal structure, the "Triads" are normally organized into five sections (Administration, Finance, Recruitment, Member Education and Operations), with no more than 120 members each (from this number of members, generally, another "Triad" is formed, with links to the first). The members are known by numbers (for the maximum leader - "Shan Chu" - the number "489"; for the head of ceremonies and initiation - "Heung Chu" - the number "426"; for the person in charge of the sector of contacts with other groups, no. "432"; for ordinary members, no. "49").

The leaders of a "Triad" can also hold leadership positions in other groups, namely those formed after the initial "Triad" was split, which, meanwhile, reached the maximum number of members - thus forming the great "TRIADES", operating at the level national and transnational.

b) Drug Trafficking

Illicit drug trafficking becomes not only the most relevant criminal activity in organized crime, but also one of its main sources of income - establishing a set of connections

with other criminal activities, such as money laundering, arms trafficking, "car crime", the diversion of precursors from the legal market, thefts and thefts.

In fact, no other activity is capable of generating so many profits, so quickly and with such low (or controlled) risks for its authors. As an example, the following data should be kept: one kilogram of heroin - base costs about 300 Euros in production (Afghanistan); after being refined, it was worth about 14 or 18 thousand Euros in any country of western destination.

This is, in fact, the decisive and catalytic element of drug trafficking: its exponential profits.

From year to year, there has been a progressive increase in the production and supply of cocaine, heroin in and hashish (among other products also trafficable) by criminal organizations - just check the increasing quantities of seized narcotic product that indicate, at least, a corresponding increase in product in circulation since, in relation to this, it is known that the percentage of product seized and removed from the market by the authorities remains at 10/15%.

On the other hand, in addition to the quantitative element in the offer, there is also a qualitative evolution of illicit drug trafficking, practiced by complex and powerful networks, characterized by the increasing sophistication of means with which they are equipped, high mobility and level of adaptation to dissuasive measures.

Cocaine

Cocaine trafficking is largely controlled by the large South American cartels, namely the Colombians from Cali, Medellin, Pereira, Costa and Valle do Norte who, acting transnational, dominate all stages of the process, from production to through transformation, up to distribution / trafficking.

Most of the coca grown in the world comes from Peru (Alto Huagalla valley) - an area that is protected by the guerrillas (which, in return, they receive from drug traffickers, money and arms). The second largest producer is Bolivia, followed by Colombia.

In recent times, due in particular to the strong pressure from the authorities, the large cartels have established new production zones in Brazil, installing refining laboratories in several other countries in Latin America (other than traditional Colombia) and changing their operations centres for Argentina, Brazil, Ecuador, Venezuela and Panama.

The main market for cocaine continues to be the U.S. (with about 6 million regular consumers). But due to the relatively low prices of cocaine in this country, due to

supply saturation, South American cartels have recently sought out other, more lucrative markets, where prices are higher - Europe and Japan.

Retain further, as an indicator of future criminal developments in this field, two elements:

- The recent appetite and entry of Italian mafia organizations ("Cosa Nostra" and "Camorra") in the cocaine trade with a European destination;
- The recent use by the Colombian cartels of the squares of Moscow and St. Petersburg, to the east, and Frankfurt, in the centre of Europe, for the development of their activities.

These situations, if they can be immediately explained by the growing importance of the European cocaine market, will also be related to the demand and control of new drug trafficking routes (through the territories of the former USSR, Bulgaria, Poland, Hungary and the Czech Republic), due to the war in the Balkans (ex-Yugoslavia) that affects the traditional route towards the markets of Northern Europe.

Heroin

The major heroin production areas (derived from opium) are located in Asia, in the so-called "Golden Triangle" (Burma, Laos and Thailand) and in the so-called "Golden Crescent" (Afghanistan, Iran and Pakistan).

The main market for heroin has been Europe (with entry from the North, namely Holland), although we are currently witnessing a strengthening of the North American and Canadian market (following the reverse process for cocaine), as well as "new" markets Asians, such as China.

Heroin trafficking is controlled and dominated by mobster-type organizations. In European terms, the most important role is played by the Italian "Mafias" (namely "Cosa Nostra", which also almost monopolizes the American market), without forgetting the intervention of the Turkish and Greek mafia groups that until now, have controlled the traditional route of entry into Europe (the Balkans), as well as the "Eastern Mafia" groups that, with the assumption of new trafficking routes to replace the now insecure route passing through the former Yugoslavia, have gained power and importance.

In any case, it should be noted that if, at the level of cocaine trafficking, a criminal organization (the cartel) controls the whole process (from production to product distribution), with heroin things are different, since, throughout the process, several organizations intervene until the product reaches the final consumer.

Also, as an indicator of possible future criminal developments in this area, retain the following elements:

- The indication that Colombia is becoming a heroin-producing country at the expense of cocaine;
- And, concomitantly, the increasing intrusion of South American cartels into the heroin trade to the U.S.
- The emergence of new production zones in territories of the former USSR (in particular in Ukraine, the Caucasus Republics and Central Asia).

CANNABIS (Hashish)

Cannabis is the best known and most consumed hallucinogen of natural origin. According to the countries or areas known as: Liamba (Angola), Suruma (Mozambique) Marijuana (Latin countries), Marijuana, (Brazil).

Hashish results mainly from the use of resin and other parts of cannabis, being produced on a larger scale in the Mediterranean basin (Morocco, Lebanon), in the entire South Asian belt to India (Iran, Afghanistan, Pakistan, Southern Republics former USSR, India, among others.), in Mexico and Central America.

The hash traffic at the international level is not dominated by any major criminal organization, but resides in its development in small national or international networks. In part, this circumstance can be explained by the negative relation of quantity - price in the distribution of the product: on the one hand, because it is by far the least profitable, it forces the traffic of large volumes that, on the other hand, introduce greater risks and difficulties of circulation and transportation to the product.

In any case, in recent years, there has been an increase in the volume of hash traffic, coming from Morocco to Europe and South Asia to the American market, preferably using the sea (50%) and land (47%).

References:

Albanese, Jay S. (2015). *Organized Crime: From the Mob to Transnational Organized Crime*. London: Routledge.

Smith, Dwight C. (1980). Paragons, Pariahs, and Pirates: A Spectrum-Based Theory of Enterprise. *Crime & Delinquency*, vol. 26, 358-386.

Pizzini-Gambetta, Valerie (2014). Organized Crime: The Gender Constraints of Illegal Markets. In R. Gartner and B. McCarthy, eds. *The Oxford Handbook of Gender, Sex, and Crime*. Oxford University Press.

Albanese, Jay S. (2008). Risk Assessment in Organized Crime: Developing a Market and Product-Based Model to Determine Threat Levels. *Journal of Contemporary Criminal Justice*, vol. 24, 11-25.

Albanese, Jay S. (2012). Deciphering the Linkages between Organized Crime and Transnational Crime. *Journal of International Affairs*, vol. 66, 1-16.

Australian Criminal Intelligence Commission. (2017). *Organised Crime in Australia*. Australian Criminal Intelligence Commission.

Barberet, Rosemary. (2014). Measuring and Researching Transnational Crime. P. Reichel and J. Albanese, eds. *Handbook of Transnational Crime and Justice*, 2d. ed. Sage.

Bisogno, Enrico. (2016). Towards Framework to Measure and Monitor Organized Crime, Illegal Economy and Illicit Financial Flows. *Transcrime*.

Carter, David L. and Jeremy G. Carter. (2009). Intelligence-Led Policing Conceptual and Functional Considerations for Public Policy. *Criminal Justice Policy Review*, vol. 20, 310-325.

Cartwright, Robin and Frances Cleland Bones. (2017). *Transnational Organized Crime and the Impact on the Private Sector: The Hidden Battalions*. Geneva: Global Initiative against Organized Crime.

Castle, Allan. (2008). Measuring the Impact of Law Enforcement on Organized Crime. *Trends in Organized Crime*, vol. 11, 135-156.

Dugato, Marco, Marco De Simoni and Ernesto Savona. (2014). *Measuring Organized Crime in Latin America*. *Transcrime*.

Criminal Intelligence Service Canada. (2007). *Integrated Threat Assessment Methodology*. Criminal Intelligence Service Canada.

Europol. (2010). *Europol Launches Scan System for Strategic Notices on Newly Identified Organised Crime Threats*

Europol. (2017). *Serious and Organised Crime Threat Assessment*. European Union.

Federal Bureau of Investigation. (2017). *Transnational Organized Crime* .

Goldstock, R., M. Marcus, T. Thacher, and J. Jacobs. (1991). *Corruption and Racketeering in the New York City Construction Industry: The Final Report of the New York State Organized Crime Task Force*. New York University Press.

Graycar, A. and M. Felson. (2010). *Situational Prevention of Organized Timber Theft and Related Corruption*. In K. Bullock, R.V. Clarke, and N. Tilley, eds. *Situational Prevention of Organised Crimes*. Devon, UK: Willan Publishing.

Hobbs, Dick. (2013). *Lush Life: Constructing Organized Crime in the UK*. Oxford University Press.

Kirby, Stuart and Laura Nailer. (2013). *Reducing the Offending of a UK Organized Crime Group using an Opportunity-reducing Framework-a Three Year Case Study*, *Trends in Organized Crime*, vol. 16, 397-412.

Klerks, Peter. (2007). *Methodological Aspects of the Dutch National Threat Assessment*. *Trends in Organized Crime*, vol. 10, 91-101.

Meško, Gorazd, Dobovšek, Bojan, Kešetović, Želimir. (2009). *Measuring Organized Crime in Slovenia*. *Problems of Post-Communism*, vol. 56, 58-62.

Midgley, Tim, Ivan Briscoe and Daniel Bertoli. (2014). *Identifying Approaches and Measuring Impacts of Programmes Focused on Transnational Organised Crime*. Geneva: Small Arms Survey.

Nelen, H. (2010). *Situational Organised Crime Prevention in Amsterdam: The Administrative Approach*. In K. Bullock, R.V. Clarke, and N. Tilley, eds. *Situational Prevention of Organised Crimes*. Devon, UK: Willan Publishing.

Ratcliffe, Jerry H., Steven J. Strang, and Ralph B. Taylor. (2014). *Assessing the Success Factors of Organized criminal groups: Intelligence challenges for strategic thinking*. *Policing: An International Journal of Police Strategies & Management*, vol. 37, 206-227.

Ratcliffe, Jerry H. (2016). *Intelligence-Led Policing*, 2d. ed. Routledge.

Savona, Ernesto U. (2006). *Measuring Organized Crime: An International Perspective*. *Forum on Crime and Society*, vol. 5, 21-33.

Savona, Ernesto U., and Sonia Stefanizzi, eds. (2010). *Measuring Human Trafficking: Complexities and Pitfalls*. Springer.

Savona, Ernesto U. (2010). *Infiltration of the Public Construction Industry by Italian Organised Crime*. In K. Bullock, R.V. Clarke, and N. Tilley, eds. *Situational Prevention of Organised Crimes*. Devon, UK: Willan Publishing.

Savona, Ernesto U., Francesco Calderone, and Alessia Maria Remmerswaal. (2011). Understudied Organized Crime Offending: A Discussion of the Canadian Situation in International Context. Ottawa: Public Safety Canada.

Savona, Ernesto, U. (2014). Organised Crime Numbers. *Global Crime*, 15(1-2), 1-9.

Sergi, Anna. (2016). A Qualitative Reading of the Ecological (dis)organisation of Criminal Associations. The Case of the 'Famiglia Basilischi' in Italy. *Trends in Organized Crime*, vol. 19, 149-174.

Shaw, Mark. (2011). Know Your Enemy: An Overview of Organized Crime Threat Assessments. International Peace Institute.

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2004). United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime and the Protocols Thereto. Vienna: UNODC.

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2009). Anti-human Trafficking Manual for Criminal Justice Practitioners. Module 5: Risk assessment in trafficking in persons investigations. Vienna: UNODC.

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2010). The Globalization of Crime: A Transnational Crime Threat Assessment. Vienna: UNODC.

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2010). Guidance on the Preparation and Use of Serious and Organized Crime Threat Assessments: The SOCTA Handbook. Vienna: UNODC.

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2012). Digest of Organized Crime Cases. Vienna: UNODC.

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2012). Transnational Organized Crime in Central America and the Caribbean: A Threat Assessment. Vienna: UNODC.

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2013). Global Study on Homicides. Vienna: UNODC.

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2013). Transnational Organized Crime in Eastern Africa: A Threat Assessment. Vienna: UNODC.

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2013). Transnational Organized Crime in West Africa: A Threat Assessment. Vienna: UNODC.

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2013). Transnational Organized Crime in East Asia and the Pacific: A Threat Assessment. Vienna: UNODC.

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2015). International Classification of Crime for Statistical Purposes (ICCS). Version 1.0. Vienna: UNODC.

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2016). The Afghan Opiate Trade and Africa: A Baseline Assessment. Vienna: UNODC.

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2016). Illicit Crop Monitoring Report .

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2017). World Drug Report. Vienna: UNODC.

U.S. Department of Justice. (2017). AlphaBay, the Largest Online 'Dark Market,' Shut Down. Washington, D.C. July 20.

Vander Beken, Tom. (2004). Risky Business: A Risk-Based Methodology to Measure Organized Crime. *Crime, Law & Social Change*, vol. 41, 471-516.

Van Dijk, Jan. (2007). Mafia markers: Assessing Organized Crime and Its Impact upon Societies. *Trends in Organized Crime*, vol. 10, 39-56.

Van de Bunt, H.G. and C.R.A. van der Schoot. (2003). Prevention of Organised Crime: A Situational Approach. The Netherlands: WODC.

van der Does de Willebois, Emile, Emily M. Halter, Robert A. Harrison, Ji Won Park, J. C. Sharman. (2011). The Puppet Masters: How the Corrupt Use Legal Structures to Hide Stolen Assets and What to Do About It. The World Bank and UNODC.

World Economic Forum. (2012). Organized Crime Enablers. Washington, DC.

Zoutendijk, Andries Johannes. (2010). Organised Crime Threat Assessments: a critical review. *Crime, Law and Social Change*, vol. 54, 63-86.